

Pan-genome Analysis of Plastids from Ericales

Aditya Vinukonda¹ and Manoj Samanta^{2,3,4}

1. Redmond High School, Redmond, WA 98052.
2. Systemix Institute, Sammamish, WA 98074.
3. Coding for Medicine LLC, Sammamish, WA 98074.
4. samanta@homolog.us

Abstract

Pangenome Research Toolkit (PGR-TK) was used to analyze the plastid sequences from the Ericales order. At the genus level, all members other than *Vaccinium* and *Rhododendron* showed standard quadripartite structures with uniform plastid lengths. *Cyclamen persicum* diverged significantly from the other members of its genus or family, and additional analysis showed it to be close to *Psedostellaria* (Caryophyllales). At the family level, phylogeny generated by PGR-TK correctly separated the genera. Other than Ericaceae, all family level plots displayed uniform quadripartite structures.

Introduction

Ericales is a large and diverse order of flowering plants within the asterid clade of eudicots, encompassing around 12,000 species [1]. This order includes a wide variety of plant types, ranging from shrubs and herbaceous plants to large trees, along with some chlorophyll-deficient carnivorous and parasitic species. This order is considered early-diverging within the core eudicots and preserves many primitive characteristics of dicotyledonous plants. Its ecological diversity makes it key to understanding the evolution of flowering plants. Additionally, several commercially important species, such as tea, cranberry, blueberry, kiwifruit, persimmon, rhododendron, and azalea, belong to this order.

APG IV currently recognizes 21 or 22 families within Ericales, depending on whether Sladeniaceae is considered a separate family or part of Pentaphragmaceae [2]. Molecular data confirmed the monophyly of this order. Notable families include Ericaceae (Heath family), Theaceae (Tea family), Primulaceae (Primrose family), and Sarraceniaceae (Sundew or Pitcher plant family). Morphologically, Ericales is highly diverse, a factor that historically contributed to the placement of its members in various unrelated orders. As a result, clarifying relationships among its families has posed a significant taxonomic challenge. Since 2002, considerable progress has been made in resolving these ambiguities and improving our understanding of the biogeography of Ericales [3–11]. The advent of complete plastid genome sequencing has further advanced research into the molecular phylogeny and biogeographical patterns of key families such as Ericaceae and Primulaceae [12–16].

The need to annotate the plastid genome before performing phylogenetic analysis is a significant limitation of the current methods. To address this, we have been exploring the potential of recently developed pan-genome tools to analyze plastid genomes. In particular,

we investigated the Pan-Genome Research Toolkit (PGR-TK), an advanced software that employs a minimizer-based approach to greatly enhance processing speed [17]. This approach enables comprehensive comparisons of entire plastid genomes and provides visual representations of similarity blocks, which offer valuable insights into evolutionary relationships among the studied families. While we successfully demonstrated its effectiveness on individual genera [18], our current focus is on assessing its utility for analyzing entire families and orders [19]. In this study, we use PGR-TK to analyze 27 genera and 13 families within Ericales, for which complete plastid sequences were available.

Results

Plastid sequences were downloaded from NCBI and split into FASTA files containing sequences from individual genera. After removing all genera with only 1 or 2 genomes, 27 genera were left. PGR-TK was run on each of these sets to identify pan-genome conservation patterns [19]. Additionally we separated all plastid sequences at the family levels and performed PGR-TK analysis on 13 Ericales families with sufficient data.

Observations at the Genus Level

PGR-TK compares all sequences against each other to find conserved segments. Subsequently it generates a visual display of the sequences with each conserved segment shown as a rectangle of a distinct color. PGR-TK also constructs a cladogram to highlight the evolutionary relationship between the genomes. In this analysis, PGR-TK profiles were visually inspected for length differences and variations in conservation patterns.

In a typical genus level PGR-TK comparison of plastids, four separate clusters of segments are seen representing long single-copy (LSC) region, short single-copy (SSC) region and two inverted repeat (IR) regions. Moreover, the IR regions are more conserved than the SSC and LSC regions, and therefore PGR-TK plots appear less fragmented in those regions. Finally, the sequences within the same genus tend to have similar lengths.

Rhododendron showed the highest divergence from this expected pattern (Table 1). *Rhododendron farrerae*, *Rhododendron latoucheae* and *Rhododendron simsii* were significantly shorter than the other species, while *Rhododendron kawakamii* was longer. Furthermore, *Rhododendron kawakamii* displayed a large segment of unusual repetitive sequences (Fig. 1).

For *Cyclamen*, one plastid (NC_068227.1, *Cyclamen persicum*) was notably distinct from the others. Interestingly, this sequence appeared different from all other members of the entire *Primulaceae* family. To investigate further, we searched a segment from NC_068227.1 at the NCBI BLAST site and found it to match several sequences from *Pseudostellaria* in the Caryophyllales order. A combined PGR-TK plot of *Pseudostellaria* and *Cyclamen* (Fig. 2) clearly shows that NC_068227.1 is a *Pseudostellaria* incorrectly identified as *Cyclamen*.

Vaccinium exhibited considerable variability. The sequences showed a great deal of variation, with some species appearing to be more closely related to *Agapetes* than to *Vaccinium* itself (Fig. 3).

The remaining genus-level PGR-TK plots closely matched the standard pattern (Table 1). However, *Androsace*, *Lysimachia*, *Impatiens* and *Primula* showed substantial variation between the sequences. The fragmentation among the sequences in the plot increases with decreased level of sequence conservation between them. *Gordonia* also shows substantial fragmentation, which is high for only three sequences.

Seventeen genera of Ericales matched this described pattern and moreover showed very little variations between the plastids (Table 1). They are *Actinidia*, *Adinandra*, *Alniphylum*, *Ardisia*, *Barringtonia*, *Clethra*, *Diospyros*, *Embelia*, *Lysimachia*, *Myrsine*, *Polyspora*, *Pterostyrax*, *Pyrenaria*, *Schima*, *Sinojackia*, *Stewartia*, *Styrax*, and *Symplocos*. *Camellia* and *Gaultheria* also showed the above pattern, but a few plastids had internal reversals of the SSC regions.

Overall, the Ericales family was relatively straightforward, except for the length and sequence variations observed in *Vaccinium* and *Rhododendron*.

Observations at the Family Level

Ericaceae

Ericaceae is a large and diverse family within Ericales, being made up of many commercially important plants such as cranberries, blueberries, and rhododendrons. Plastid sequences were available for *Vaccinium*, *Agapetes*, *Gaultheria*, *Rhododendron* and *Pyrola*. The cladogram generated by PGR-TK correctly separated these plants according to their known subfamilies. The plastids from the Vacciniodeae subfamily (*Vaccinium*, *Agapetes*, *Gaultheria*) formed one group, *Rhododendron* from the Ericoideae subfamily formed a second group and a single *Pyrola* plastid from Pyroloideae formed an external outgroup.

Aside from *Rhododendron* and *Vaccinium*, the plastid sequences appeared relatively consistent when compared across genera, showing similar structural patterns with only a few notable anomalies.

Styraceae

Styraceae is a relatively small family within *Ericales*, consisting primarily of ornamental trees and shrubs, along with a few species of medicinal importance. The plastid sequences within this family were largely conserved, with certain variations unique to specific genera. Despite this variation, several regions of the plastid genome were highly conserved across all sampled genera. Notably, sequences from *Styrax japonicus* and *Styrax macrocarpus* both exhibited a region in which the sequence appeared inverted, suggesting a potential structural rearrangement specific to these taxa (Fig. 4).

Primulaceae

Known commonly as the primrose family, primulaceae was once part of a different order called primulales before being merged with ericales later. The sequences in this family were largely similar to each other, holding similar patterns across sequences in a genus or even

across multiple genera. However, one of the *cyclamen* sequences stood out significantly from the others (Fig. 5).

Theaceae

Otherwise known as the tea family, theaceae seemed to have little variation for the most part. Most of the sequences were similar in their patterns, with the exception of two sequences in the *Camellia* genus (*C. brevistyla* and *C. liberistyloides*).

Actinidiaceae

Actinidiaceae was composed mostly of the genus *Actinidia*, except two from the genus *Saurauia* and one from *Clematoclethra*. All the genera were able to separate out correctly, and the plot was simple.

Lecythidaceae

Lecythidaceae had 4 sequences, 3 belonging to the genus *Barringtonia* and 1 belonging to the genus *Bertholletia*. Although *Barringtonia* showed little variation at a genus level, it showed extensive variation at a family level, meaning the addition of the different genus made a significant difference.

Balsaminaceae

This plot consisted of a single genus - *Impatiens*. Although the other sequences in this plot showed little variation, *Impatiens Morsei* has a lot more variation and is a lot shorter, which is probably the result of an erroneous sequence.

Sarraceniaceae, Pentaphragaceae

These two families had relatively simple plots, though the rectangles in the plots were smaller on average, meaning more variation/distinction from each sequence.

Sapotaceae

Overall plot of this family with six genera was simple. Two *Pouteria* sequences did not group together.

Clethraceae, Ebenaceae, Symplocaceae

Each family has only one genus in the family-level PGR-TK plots. Therefore, the family-level plots did not provide any additional insight.

Discussion

Visual analysis

Until the late 1980s, plant classification was based primarily on morphological and anatomical characteristics, such as flower structure, leaf shape, and cellular features. This approach, while foundational to botanical science, was inherently subjective and heavily reliant on the interpretive skills of individual taxonomists. The advent of DNA sequencing revolutionized plant systematics by introducing a more objective, precise, and reproducible framework grounded in molecular data and quantitative analysis [1].

Despite its advantages, molecular systematics presents a challenge to traditional, morphology-based taxonomy. The two approaches, molecular and morphological, often operate in parallel, with limited integration. The PGR-TK platform aims to bridge this divide by combining the analytical rigor of molecular methods with the intuitive clarity of visual interpretation. It enables users to explore plastid genome data both quantitatively and visually, facilitating a synthesis of data-driven precision and traditional botanical insight.

Cyclamen error

A clear example of the value of our approach can be seen in the analysis of *Cyclamen*. Of the four sequences examined, one differed significantly from the others. Even when placed at the family level, this sequence remained an outlier (Fig. 5). To investigate further, we performed a BLAST search using the NCBI database. As expected, the sequence matched *Cyclamen*, confirming its reported origin, but it also aligned closely with a distantly related genus from the order *Caryophyllales* (Fig. 2), well outside the *Ericales*.

When we visualized the two genera together using PGR-TK, the anomaly became immediately apparent, strongly suggesting a sequencing or annotation error. This case highlights a key strength of our method: the ability to detect inconsistencies visually, which can then be validated through external tools such as BLAST and further in-platform analysis.

Length difference in *Rhododendron* and Sequence difference in *Vaccinium*, Partial reversions

Overall, *Ericales* displayed expected phylogenetic patterns, with most plots following standard trends. However, a few deviations were observed, including instances of partial reversion—an occurrence we have noted in other analyses as well. These reversions typically involve the inversion of the small single-copy (SSC) region of the plastid genome, resulting in two isoforms. Some sequences appear to represent the alternate isoform, contributing to apparent variation.

Within the genus *Rhododendron*, we observed unusually high sequence variability, which may be attributed to sequencing or assembly errors (Fig. 1). Notable differences were also found in *Rhododendron* and *Vaccinium*, particularly in the lengths of certain amino acid sequences. Additionally, intra-genus sequence divergence was detected, which is uncommon at the genus level and may reflect underlying technical artifacts or previously unrecognized genetic diversity.

Sapotaceae, Primulaceae less complex than others

At the family level, we observed some unexpected phylogenetic patterns. Notably, in the families Sapotaceae and *Primulaceae*, certain genera did not form cohesive clades, with some members failing to group together as anticipated. Although the underlying causes of these discrepancies are not yet clear, they warrant further investigation and may reveal insights into lineage divergence, sequencing errors, or taxonomic misclassification.

Figures

Figure 1. PGR-TK comparison for *Rhododendron*. This plot shows significant length and sequence differences among the members of this genus.

Figure 2. PGR-TK Analysis of *Cyclamen* (Ericales) and *Pseudostellaria* (Caryophyllales). This figure suggests that NC_068227.1 is incorrectly identified as *Cyclamen persicum* in the NCBI database.

Figure 3. PGR-TK comparison of *Vaccinium*. This plot shows significant length and sequence differences among the members of this genus.

Genus	Family	Pattern Class (based on Ref 19)	Comment
<i>Actinidia</i>	Actinidiaceae	1	
<i>Adinandra</i>	Pentaphragaceae	1	
<i>Alniphyllum</i>	Styracaceae	1	
<i>Androsace</i>	Primulaceae	2	
<i>Ardisia</i>	Primulaceae	1	
<i>Barringtonia</i>	Lecythidaceae	1	
<i>Camellia</i>	Theaceae	1	
<i>Clethra</i>	Clethraceae	1	
<i>Cyclamen</i>	Primulaceae	3	Mostly fine except for one mislabeled sequence
<i>Diospyros</i>	Ebenaceae	1	
<i>Embelia</i>	Primulaceae	1	
<i>Gaultheria</i>	Ericaceae	1	
<i>Gordonia</i>	Theaceae	2	
<i>Impatiens</i>	Balsaminaceae	2	
<i>Lysimachia</i>	Primulaceae	1	
<i>Myrsine</i>	Primulaceae	1	
<i>Polyspora</i>	Theaceae	1	
<i>Primula</i>	Primulaceae	2	
<i>Pterostyrax</i>	Styracaceae	1	
<i>Pyrenaria</i>	Theaceae	1	
<i>Rhododendron</i>	Ericaceae	4	High variation with some sequences being significantly shorter than others, and one sequence containing small repeating region
<i>Schima</i>	Theaceae	1	
<i>Sinojackia</i>	Styracaceae	1	
<i>Stewartia</i>	Theaceae	1	
<i>Styrax</i>	Styracaceae	1	
<i>Symplocos</i>	Symplocaceae	1	
<i>Vaccinium</i>	Ericaceae	4	High amount of variation between sequences

Table 1. PGR-TK Patterns of Genera within Ericales. This table summarizes the patterns observed among various PGR-TK plots from 27 genera of Ericales. The pattern classes are described in Ref [19]. Additional comments are provided for some genera.

References

1. Ericales [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jul 3]. Available from: <https://www.mobot.org/MOBOT/research/APweb/orders/ericalesweb.htm#Ericales>
2. Chase MW, Christenhusz MJM, Fay MF, Byng JW, Judd WS, Soltis DE, et al. An update of the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group classification for the orders and families of flowering plants: APG IV. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society*. 2016 Apr 6;181(1):1–20.
3. Anderberg AA, Rydin C, Källersjö M. Phylogenetic relationships in the order Ericales s.l.: Analyses of molecular data from five genes from the plastid and mitochondrial genomes. *American Journal of Botany*. 2002 Apr;89(4):677–87.
4. Schönenberger J, Anderberg AA, Sytsma KJ. Molecular phylogenetics and patterns of floral evolution in the ericales. *International Journal of Plant Sciences*. 2005 Mar;166(2):265–88.
5. Lens F, Schönenberger J, Baas P, Jansen S, Smets E. The role of wood anatomy in phylogeny reconstruction of Ericales. *Cladistics*. 2007 Mar 21;23(3):229–94.
6. Schönenberger J, von Balthazar M, Sytsma KJ. Diversity and evolution of floral structure among early diverging lineages in the Ericales. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 2010 Feb 12;365(1539):437–48.
7. Löffstrand SD, Schönenberger J. Molecular phylogenetics and floral evolution in the sarracenioid clade (Actinidiaceae, Roridulaceae and Sarraceniaceae) of Ericales. *TAXON*. 2015 Dec;64(6):1209–24.
8. Rose JP, Kleist TJ, Löffstrand SD, Drew BT, Schönenberger J, Sytsma KJ. Phylogeny, historical biogeography, and diversification of angiosperm order Ericales suggest ancient Neotropical and East Asian connections. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 2018 May;122:59–79.
9. Larson DA, Walker JF, Vargas OM, Smith SA. A consensus phylogenomic approach highlights paleopolyploid and rapid radiation in the history of Ericales. *American Journal of Botany*. 2020 Apr 29;107(5):773–89.
10. Chartier M, von Balthazar M, Sontag S, Löffstrand S, Palme T, Jabbour F, et al. Global patterns and a latitudinal gradient of flower disparity: Perspectives from the angiosperm order Ericales. *New Phytologist*. 2021 Mar 4;230(2):821–31.
11. Herting J, Schönenberger J, Sauquet H. Profile of a flower: How rates of morphological evolution drive floral diversification in Ericales [Internet]. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory; 2022 Nov [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.11.28.518258>
12. Chin CS, Behera S, Khalak A, Sedlazeck FJ, Sudmant PH, Wagner J, et al.

Multiscale analysis of pangenomes enables improved representation of genomic diversity for repetitive and clinically relevant genes. *Nature Methods*. 2023 Jun 26;20(8):1213–21.

13. Jayanti R, Kim A, Pham S, Raghavan A, Sharma A, Samanta MP. arXiv.org. 2023. Comparative analysis of plastid genomes using pangenome research toolkit (PGR-TK). Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2310.19110>

14. Samanta MP. arXiv.org. 2025. Pan-genome Analysis of Angiosperm Plastomes using PGR-TK. Available from: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.20034>

15. Mao L, Zou Q, Sun Z, Dong Q, Cao X. Insights into chloroplast genome structure, intraspecific variation, and phylogeny of *Cyclamen* species (Myrsinoideae). *Scientific Reports*. 2023 Jan 3;13(1).

16. Logacheva MD, Schelkunov MI, Shtratnikova VY, Matveeva MV, Penin AA. Comparative analysis of plastid genomes of non-photosynthetic Ericaceae and their photosynthetic relatives. *Scientific Reports*. 2016 Jul 25;6(1).

17. Freudenstein JV, Broe MB, Feldenkris ER. Phylogenetic relationships at the base of Ericaceae: Implications for vegetative and mycorrhizal evolution. *TAXON*. 2016 Aug;65(4):794–804.

18. Becker A, Crowl AA, Luteyn JL, Chanderbali AS, Judd WS, Manos PS, et al. A global blueberry phylogeny: Evolution, diversification, and biogeography of tribe vaccinieae (ericaceae) [Internet]. Elsevier BV; 2024 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837226>

19. Kriebel R, Rose JP, Bastide P, Jolles D, Reginato M, Sytsma KJ. The evolution of Ericaceae flowers and their pollination syndromes at a global scale. *American Journal of Botany*. 2023 Sep;110(9).

20. Yan M, Fritsch PW, Moore MJ, Feng T, Meng A, Yang J, et al. Plastid phylogenomics resolves infrafamilial relationships of the Styracaceae and sheds light on the backbone relationships of the Ericales. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 2018 Apr;121:198–211.

21. Song Y, Zhao W, Xu J, Li M, Zhang Y. Chloroplast genome evolution and species identification of *styrax* (styracaceae). *BioMed Research International*. 2022 Jan;2022(1).

22. Larson DA, Chanderbali AS, Maurin O, Gonçalves DJP, Dick CW, Soltis DE, et al. The phylogeny and global biogeography of Primulaceae based on high-throughput DNA sequence data. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 2023 May;182:107702.

23. Wang Y, Li J, Fan Z, Wu D, Yin H, Li X. Characterization of the complete chloroplast genome of *Camellia brevistyla*, an oil-rich and evergreen shrub. *Mitochondrial DNA Part B*. 2020 Jan 2;5(1):386–7.

24. Cheng L, Li M, Han Q, Qiao Z, Hao Y, Balbuena TS, et al. Phylogenomics Resolves the Phylogeny of Theaceae by Using Low-Copy and Multi-Copy Nuclear Gene Markers and Uncovers a Fast Radiation Event Contributing to Tea Plants Diversity - PMC. *Biology*. 11(7).